

The future of India's Thermal Power

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Abstract: Rising electricity demand and the need to strike a balance between energy security and environmental sustainability are projected to force significant changes in India's thermal power scenario in the years to come. In order to satisfy the increasing demand, India has revised its objective to add 80 GW of coal-fired power capacity over the next six years. By 2030, the nation wants to generate 500 GW of non-fossil fuel capacity and 10 GW of geothermal power. By 2034–2035, India will need about 1,981,000 MWh of energy storage capacity, with pumped hydro storage (PSH) and battery energy storage systems (BESS) being the vital options. In order to achieve India's target of net-zero carbon emissions, thermal power will continue to play a significant role until 2035, at which point its capacity will be gradually reduced in favour of renewable energy. This study will offer opinions on how to guarantee a steady supply of electricity to sustain India's fast urbanization and economic expansion. Modernize transmission infrastructure, increase energy storage capacity, and diversify the mix of power sources.

Keywords: Thermal Power, Renewable Energy, Operational Strategy

Introduction

Maintaining development and raising living standards in India requires a steady and dependable energy supply as the country continues on its path of fast economic growth. An important part of India's energy mix, thermal power is essential to supplying the nation's growing energy needs. In light of India's changing energy landscape and dedication to sustainable development, this conversation examines the advantages, difficulties, and potential future of thermal power in relation to the country's economic progress. Thermal power's role will continue to change as India manages its energy transition. India has set lofty goals for renewable energy capacity, which would progressively change the energy mix. The country wants to increase the share of renewable energy. Improve energy efficiency: It will be essential to lower transmission losses and increase the efficiency of thermal power plants. Adopt cleaner technology: India is investigating carbon capture and storage options as well as cleaner coal technologies. Given the interdependence of energy security, economic growth, and environmental sustainability, it is imperative to assess the role of thermal power in India's economic prosperity going forward. Some of the major Aspects are as follows, Coal-based thermal power: Coal-fired power plants generate a sizable portion of India's electricity, making up the majority of the country's thermal power industry. Generation and capacity: India's total thermal power capacity is around 240 GW [1], of which about 74.66% comes from coal-based plants during 2023-24 [2]. Regional distribution: States like Jharkhand, Odisha, and Chhattisgarh, which have substantial coal supplies, are home to the majority of thermal power plants. Challenges: Coal shortages and power plant outages are the result of India's coal production not keeping up with demand. Environmental issues: The production of thermal electricity increases greenhouse gas emissions, water pollution, and air pollution. The findings of this study will aid in highlighting strategies and obstacles facing India's thermal power sector, which have a significant influence on the country and its citizens. It would support numerous advancements and prospects in research institutes and industry both in India and abroad. Artificial Intelligence, Digitalization, Modernization, Automation, Greenolution—Renewable Energy—and other innovations where energy is a critical necessity are the main topics of discussion in the era of Industry 4.0. Reliable power is a crucial component in ensuring energy security [3]. Given their crucial role in power generation and sustainability, the difficulties faced by thermal power plants make for an interesting subject of study.

Literature Review

The development of the country depends on electricity. Given the steadily rising demand, it is imperative to make sure that energy addition and sustainability plans are in place to satisfy the demand and guarantee that the nation's citizens have a steady supply of electricity. The growth history of the Indian power sector has been examined in order to examine this topic in greater detail. examined India's present power situation, future expansion strategy, and energy mix forecast. investigated every facet of the many sources, including thermal, solar, wind, nuclear, hydro, and bio. Reviewing strategies is essential to ensuring power reliability for everyone by identifying issues and developing appropriate mitigation plans. In 1947, the year of India's independence, we saw the development of 508 MW of hydropower and 854 MW of thermal power. [1].

Table 1. key aspects and findings in thermal power research:

SI.No	Aspect	Key Findings	References
1	Energy Efficiency	Energy and exergy analysis can identify areas of inefficiency in thermal power plants.	Rosen & Dincer (2003) [4]
2	Exergy Destruction	Boiler irreversibility is a major contributor to exergy destruction in coal-fired thermal power plants	Rosen & Dincer (2003) [4]
3	Cleaner Coal Technologies	Advanced coal combustion technologies can reduce emissions and improve efficiency.	IEA Clean Coal Centre [6]
4	Geothermal Thermal Power	Closed-loop geothermal systems can enhance thermal power extraction from deep reservoirs.	Wang et., al (2022) [7]
5	Carbon Capture and Storage	CCS can reduce CO ₂ emissions from thermal power plants, but faces technical and economic challenges	IPCC (2018) [8]

Here are some operational challengers identified by respective researchers.

1. Fuel Quality Issues: Variability in fuel quality can affect combustion efficiency, slagging, and fouling [Spliethoff, H. (2010). Power Generation from Solid Fuels]. [10]
2. Slagging and Fouling: Deposits on heat transfer surfaces can reduce efficiency and increase maintenance [Raask, E. (1985). Mineral Impurities in Coal Combustion.]. [11]
3. Corrosion and Erosion: Corrosion and erosion of equipment can lead to premature wear and tear [Dooley, R. B., & McNaughton, K. (2015). Flow-Accelerated Corrosion in Power Plants.]. [12]
4. Ash Handling Issues: Ash disposal and handling can be problematic, especially with high-ash coal [Kumar, S., & Mohapatra, S. K. (2017). Ash Handling in Thermal Power Plants]. [13]
5. Cooling System Issues: Cooling system performance can impact plant efficiency and reliability [El-Dessouky, H. T., & Ettouney, H. M. (2002). Fundamentals of Salt Water Desalination]. [14]
6. Control System Challenges: Complex control systems require precise tuning to optimize performance [Åström, K. J., & Hägglund, T. (2006). Advanced PID Control]. [15]
7. Maintenance and Repair: Regular maintenance and repair are crucial to prevent equipment failures [Moblely, R. K. (2001). Plant Engineer's Handbook]. [16]

Current Status of Indian Thermal Power Industry

Growth of Thermal and Renewable Power Sector

Year on Year % Growth data for Thermal and Renewable has been calculated and plotted in Figure-1. It can be reviewed that Y-on-Y growth in Renewable Energy (RE) is above 10 % since around last 10 years where as Y-on-Y % growth in Thermal is continuously reducing and observed below 10% in last 10 years. This data has been calculated as per following calculation method from raw historical data from NPP dashboard [1]

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ Growth for 2015} = (\text{MW in 2015} - \text{MW in 2014}) \times 100 / \text{MW in 2014}$$

$$\% \text{ Growth of Thermal in 2015} = (188898 - 168255) \times 100 / 188898 = 12.27 \%$$

$$\% \text{ Growth of RE in 2025} = (38959 - 34988) \times 100 / 38959 = 11.35 \%$$

Calculation has been done for last 10 years.

Contribution Comparison on Thermal, Renewable, Hydro & Nuclear

For last 10 years, % contribution from Thermal, Renewable, Hydro & Nuclear have been calculated and plotted in Figure – 2. Calculated data indicates that % contribution from Thermal is continuously reducing from 68.71 % in 2015 to 52.79 % in 2024 whereas RE is continuously increasing from 14.17 % in 2015 to 35.25 % in 2024.

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ Contribution} = 100 \times (\text{MW of respective contributor for respective year}) / \text{Total MW}$$

$$\% \text{ Contribution from Thermal for 2015} = 100 \times 188898 \text{ MW} / 274904 \text{ MW} = 68.71 \%$$

$$\% \text{ Contribution from RE for 2015} = 100 \times 38959 \text{ MW} / 274904 \text{ MW} = 14.17 \%$$

Figure – 1: Year-on-Year Growth in % for Thermal and Renewable Power Sector

Fig – 2: % contribution from different source

Continual increment in power demand

Per capita energy consumption is constantly rising from 566.69 KWH in 2002-03 to 1331 KWH in 2022-23 [17]. Due to modernization, industrialization, lifestyle & cultural change, advancement, electrical consumption is continuously increasing. Figure – 3, Per Capita consumption trend shows, power requirement is constantly increasing. [18]. India's electricity demand is projected to peak at 273 GW in June 2025, driven by increased cooling needs during summer months. The country's electricity consumption surged by nearly 7% to 148.48 billion units in March 2025. [5]

Major consumer of electricity:

For 2022-23, major consumers are Industrial which consumes 41.23%, Domestic – 24.52%, Agriculture - 16.93 %, Commercial 8.14 %, Public Water Works 2.15% and others consumes 6.69 % of total electricity consumption [17]. So maximum consumption is being observed in Industrial sector. Trend of 24 years electricity consumption [19] indicates that all categories, energy consumption is being continuously increasing. Industrial Consumption is highest and increased rapidly and continuously. Power Consumption will increase accordingly.

Greenolution – Renewable Energy (Way to overcome the challenge)

United Nations have stated aspirations for Sustainable Energy for All. For sustainable development, the resolution emphasized the need to increase access to energy services and supplies that are dependable, reasonably priced, economically feasible, socially acceptable, and environmentally sound. [20]. India has announced its ambition to achieve net zero by 2070 [21]. Developing countries have determined aspiring target for raising RE to reduce energy imports, in line with their projected economic growth and requirement. [22]. The return-to-RE is the great approach, but it must be sustainable to ensure that future generations can meet energy needs. [23]. India is a moderately energy-poor nation with significant provincial disparities in energy access. [24]. India is at a pivotal juncture in its energy transformation with the dual objective of sustaining economic development and honouring environmental goal [25]. To achieve net zero emission [26] target, world’s major countries are emphasizing on Renewable Energy (RE). India has also Perceived exponential installation progress in the field of Green Energy.

Fig – 3 Per Capita Energy Consumption [17][18]
Fig – 4 % Electricity Consumption (17)

As on 31st March 2022, RE Source installed capacity from Solar (34%), large hydro (30%), Wind (26%), Biomass (7%) and small hydro (3%) . Solar addition is 76% of total RES observed from data of capacity addition 2017-22 (as on 31st March 2022) [27]

Table – 2: Installed RE Capacity as on 31-Mar-22 and RE addition 2017-22 [27]

RE Source	Installed RE Capacity 31.03.2022		RE Capacity addition 2017 – 22 (31.03.2022)	
	MW	%	MW	%
Solar	53996.54 MW	34 %	41707.72 MW	76 %
Large Hydro	46722.52 MW	30 %	2138 MW	4 %
Small Hydro	4839.39 MW	3 %	469.04 MW	1 %
Biomass	10682.36 MW	7 %	2386.58 MW	4 %
Wind	40357.58 MW	26 %	8077.81 MW	15 %

The Government is making efforts to harness the available potential through various schemes and programs like Solar Parks, Viability Gap Funding (VGF), Rooftop Solar, PM-KUSUM, National Programme on high efficiency Solar PV Modules and Green Energy Corridor Scheme for Intra-State Transmission System, launched online portal for information & promotion of RE [28]. States also promote RE with policy support.

Power Generation Mix Prediction

Government is planning to add electricity generation through multiple appropriate resources to meet power demand to ensure uninterrupted growth of Nation and to fulfil basic requirements. From all sources, electricity addition shall be enhanced but % growth will differ for different sources. Electricity supply from coal source will be continually increased from 994.2 TWh in 2022 to 3212.71 TWh in 2047 [29] [30]. Table – 3, indicates projection from different source.

Table 3 Sourcewise energy supply projection IESS 2047 V3.0

Source	Projection Year (Trillion-watt hours TWh)				
	2027	2032	2037	2042	2047
Gas	50.09	51.24	52.39	53.54	54.69
Coal	1303.75	1657.39	1984.84	2454.98	3212.71
CCS	0	8.59	17.18	25.77	34.36
Nuclear	72.7	106.82	156.96	230.62	338.86
Hydro	183.68	206.07	226.59	230.57	234.56
Solar	176.34	349.09	593.51	873.98	1143.87
Wind	126.85	237.66	464.8	770.11	1097.43
Bioenergy	20.41	22.13	24.26	26.96	29.39
Electricity trade	0.4	5.68	13.72	17.51	22.35
Total	1934.22	2644.67	3534.24	4684.06	6168.23

Electricity generation plan indicates in 2047 during Azadi ka Amritkal, Thermal Power contribution shall be around 52 % [29] it means Thermal will be backbone of power grid.

Fig-5: Sourcewise electricity supply IESS 2047

Fig – 5, explains Thermal Power volume in year 2047 will be highest with compare to other source of energy [29]. Volume of RE will be significant but still backbone will be Thermalwith consideration of major contributor and reliable source of energy.

Conclusion

India's electricity consumption is expected to triple by 2050, making it the third-largest electricity consumer in the world [9]. By implementing Mix power generation with flexible operation can be improved. The various advantage are Energy Security: By reducing reliance on a single source, diversifying power sources helps to ensure a steady supply of energy. Renewable Integration: Using renewable energy sources, such as hydroelectric, wind, and solar power, lowers greenhouse gas emissions and slows down global warming. Resilience: By offering backup choices in the event of outages or disruptions, a diverse power generation portfolio improves system resilience. Economic Benefits: A well-balanced mix of power sources can lower price volatility, optimize energy expenses, and spur economic expansion. Environmental Benefits: A diverse power generation portfolio helps lower air and water pollution by utilizing cleaner energy sources.

The challenges on this will be Complexity of Integration: Complex grid management and infrastructure are needed to integrate various electricity sources. Cost and Investment: A substantial investment is needed to build and maintain a portfolio of diversified power generating. Policy and Regulation: To promote the growth of a varied power generation mix, supportive policies and regulations are required. The optimal mix of power generation sources varies depending on regional factors like resource availability, energy demand, and environmental concerns. A balanced mix might include:

1. Renewable Energy: Solar, wind, hydroelectric, and other renewable sources.
2. Fossil Fuels: Coal, Natural gas, and oil, with a focus on cleaner technologies.
3. Nuclear Power: A low-carbon source that can provide baseload power.
4. Energy Storage: Technologies like batteries and pumped hydro storage to stabilize the grid.

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